

Restorative Justice Breakthrough By The Prosecutors To Maximize Terrorism Prevention Effort

Pujiyono, Seniwati, Sufmi Dasco Ahmad, Arfin Sudirman

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 09, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 12, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Terrorisme; Prevention; Prosecutors; Restorative Justice</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5565116</p>	<p><i>The process of punishing perpetrators of criminal acts of terrorism starts from the process of investigation, investigation, prosecution to court decisions to become one unit in law enforcement. Before terrorism convicts go through the final stages and are found guilty so that the correctional institution as a place that has a role in providing guidance to terrorist prisoners not to repeat their actions, the initial effort that should be done is to maximize prevention. The absence of a strong legal umbrella for intelligence activities to support efforts to prevent and counter terrorism and a narrow understanding while religious communities, plus traditional communities facing economic and social problems are very easily influenced or recruited to become members of terrorist groups. This is strengthened by the handling of criminal acts that prioritize violence, which makes terrorism harder and leads to revenge. It takes a breakthrough effort in the form of Restorative Justice by the Prosecutor's Office, so that the process before going to court can end up being mutually beneficial.</i></p>

Introduction

Indonesia has local wisdom in resolving disputes or conflicts, namely prioritizing deliberation in making decisions for the common good. Deliberations to reach consensus are filled with the spirit of kinship. Deliberation contains 5 (five) principles as follows: first, conferencing (meeting to hear each other and express wishes); second, search solutions (looking for solutions or common ground for the problems at hand); third, reconciliation (to make peace with each other's responsibilities); fourth, repair (repair all the consequences that arise); and fifth, circles (support each other).

Crime prevention policies should always be able to follow the development of the crime itself because legal developments result in the development of criminal methods and vice versa. One type of crime that continues to grow and is a concern both globally and nationally in this nation is the crime of terrorism. Terrorism crimes are even included in the National Legislation Program, both in the Draft Criminal Code Bill (RUU KUHP) and in the revision of the Terrorism Law because the public considers the existing regulations to be incapable and maximal in tackling terrorism crimes. Examining the crime of terrorism, in principle, cannot be separated from the main problem, namely as a form of crime (crime). According to Ali Masyar, global crimes occur due to arbitrary actions carried out by most countries through their government apparatus, such as often causing disappointment, even the most extreme is the emergence of radicalism in certain countries or groups who feel oppressed. Radical acts like this are what eventually give rise to acts of terror or terrorism. Criminal punishment for terrorists in positive law in Indonesia is not only imposed on the main perpetrators such as the perpetrators of the bombing or murder, but also on people who are related to the perpetrators of the crime, for example. people who intentionally provide assistance or convenience to perpetrators, or provide money or financial support to perpetrators, people who hide terrorist actors or people who hide information about criminal acts of terrorism as regulated in Article 13 of Law Number 15 of 2003 concerning Eradication of Crimes Terrorism.

Criminal acts of terrorism are activities that contain elements of violence or which have dangerous consequences for human life and of course these activities violate the criminal law, and are clearly intended to intimidate the civilian population; influence the policy and administration of the state by kidnapping and killing. The dangerous consequences for example, can be in the form of casualties, both life, physical, property, psychological, and psycho-social. Meanwhile, according to Hery Firmansyah, the crime of terrorism is defined as a transnational crime, organized, and even an international crime that has a network, which threatens national and international peace and security.

In Indonesia, restorative justice is not a new concept because the concept of customary law in Indonesia as a forum for customary justice institutions also has a concept that can be described as the root of restorative justice. The characteristics of customary law in each region are generally very supportive of the application of restorative justice. This can be seen from the general characteristics of Indonesian customary law, views on customary violations/customary offenses as well as the models and solutions offered. Restorative

justice has the meaning of restoring justice. Restoration has a broader meaning than what is known in the conventional criminal justice process as restitution or compensation for victims. This is seen from the view that in a crime event, the suffering of the person who has become the victim does not only result in the person himself, but also affects the people around him. It even has an impact on society and the country in a wider scope. In criminal justice practice, victims are only needed or positioned as witnesses (victims), without the right to take an active role in court proceedings. Law enforcement officers only place victims as instruments in order to help them to punish or impose criminal penalties on perpetrators, without ever proceeding with they gave for the benefit of the victim.

Restorative justice does not merely implement decisions about who wins and who loses in an adversarial criminal justice system, the restorative justice process seeks a facility for dialogue between all parties affected by crime including victims, perpetrators, perpetrators and perpetrators, supporters, and society as a whole. This involves a process in which all parties at risk in a particular crime come together to work out collectively how to deal with the aftermath of a crime and its future implications. It is interesting to discuss the potential for the application of restorative justice by the prosecutor to maximize prevention in Indonesia.

A. RESEARCH METHOD

Normative legal research uses normative case studies in the form of legal behavior products, for example examining laws. The main point of the study is the law conceptualized as norms or rules that apply in society and become a reference for everyone's behavior. So that normative legal research focuses on the inventory of positive law, legal principles and doctrines, legal findings in concrete cases, legal systematic, level of synchronization, comparative law and legal history. Based on the explanation above, the authors decided to use normative legal research methods to research and write a discussion of this paper as a legal research method. This research consists of binding library materials which are primary and secondary legal materials. Primary legal materials are: the Criminal Code, the Criminal Procedure Code, and Law Number 5 of 2018 concerning the Eradication of Terrorism. Secondary legal materials consist of books, legal journals, legal theories, expert opinions and legal research results. Meanwhile, tertiary legal materials are articles from the internet. The data that has been obtained are then analyzed through a qualitative analysis approach,

B. DISCUSSION

1. Prosecutors' cooperation in countering terrorism

Countering terrorism in Indonesia is carried out with a targeted and comprehensive strategy through a national strategy that contains targets and policy directions for countering terrorism based on existing regulations. The terrorism prevention and countermeasure program involves various government agencies and all components of the nation's power. The problem of terrorism can only be solved through cooperation and coordination between various stakeholders, both government agencies and the community. For this reason, the National Army, the Prosecutors General's Office and the Police will continue to conduct joint simulations considering the importance of such cooperation. To assist in handling cases related to terrorism, the Prosecutors General's Office has established a task force for handling criminal acts of terrorism and transnational crimes so that it is hoped that the settlement of terrorism cases can be carried out better.

The Prosecutors General's Office signed a memorandum of understanding between the National Counterterrorism Agency (BNPT) regarding coordination and cooperation in countering terrorism. The signing of a memorandum of understanding (MoU) was carried out by the two leaders of the institution in order to cope with the growth and development of various radical ideas and acts and aggressive acts of terror that are increasingly occurring. including the establishment of the Directorate of Terrorism Crimes and Transnational Crimes, which initially was only a Task Force. It is hoped that the attention and handling of the problem of terrorism, both in the form of prevention and action in an integrated manner with all related parties, can be carried out more optimally. In addition, attention is still needed on other important matters, namely a comprehensive policy from upstream to downstream regarding prevention, prosecution to recovery and post-action guidance related to solving this one problem, so that all parties, Ministries and Institutions who have duties, responsibilities and the function of dealing with it can synergize, coordinate and cooperate more intensely and integrated, each of which together can act more clearly in completing the prevention and handling of the terrorism network in question to its roots.

Agreements and cooperative relationships that are not only motivated by a desire but more than that, because of the encouragement of a need to build commitment and joint efforts to strengthen and facilitate cooperative coordination relations between the Prosecutor's Office and BNPT in a spirit and atmosphere of mutual support, complement and strengthen each other in order to build capabilities, potentials, and conducive atmosphere in the implementation of tasks, authorities and responsibilities, particularly with regard to countermeasures, prevention and eradication of acts of terrorism. The purpose and objective of this collaboration is to optimize law enforcement for criminal acts of terrorism and combat the spread of radicalism as the basis for synergizing the implementation of counter-terrorism in Indonesia. In addition, this collaboration

is carried out to exchange data on the spread of terrorism and counter terrorism. This collaboration also aims to disseminate information to the general public regarding the prevention of the spread of terrorism teachings.

2. Efforts to Use Restorative Justice

The restorative justice movement has grown rapidly in the last twenty-five years. It is estimated that there are about 1,000 restorative justice programs in the world and at least eighty countries have adopted some form of restorative justice program in response to the problem of crime. At this time Restorative justice represents a paradigm shift in the way Americans conceptualize and administer punishment. As part of initiatives for criminal justice reform, restorative justice has been largely taken up in countries with Western legal systems, especially those with common law and civil law traditions in response to conventional limitations. For informal justice to be restorative justice, about restoring victims, restoring perpetrators, and restoring society as a result of the participation of a plurality of stakeholders. Regulatory theory (responsive regulatory pyramids) may be more useful for preventing crime in a normatively acceptable manner than existing criminal law jurisprudence and explanatory theory. Evidence-based reforms must move toward a more productive examination of restorative justice by liberal legalism, and vice versa.

The legal umbrella for handling terrorism is Law Number 5 of 2018 concerning Amendments to Law Number 5 of 2003 concerning Stipulation of Government Regulations in Lieu of Law Number 1 of 2002 concerning Eradication of Criminal Acts of Terrorism into Law. Efforts to reform the law are motivated by an increase in terror events that occur in Indonesia, reflecting that law enforcement efforts alone are not enough to stop or at least reduce the occurrence of criminal acts of terrorism. Thus, more appropriate prevention efforts are needed to overcome the seeds of radicalism that have the potential to become criminal acts of terrorism. Some changes or additions to the content material in Law Number 5 of 2018 still require implementing regulations.

The shift in punishment in the criminal justice system prioritizes justice for victims and perpetrators of criminal acts in addition to alternative punishments such as social work and others which are carried out with a restorative justice approach. Focusing on the process of direct criminal accountability from the perpetrator to the victim and the community, if the perpetrator and victim and the community whose rights have been violated feel that justice has been achieved through joint deliberation efforts, then punishment can be avoided. The perpetrator is not the main object of the restorative justice approach, but the sense of justice and conflict recovery itself is the main object. The Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia on December 22, 2020 through the Director General of the General Judiciary Agency has issued Decision Number: 1691 / DJU / SK / PS.00 / 12/2020 concerning the Application of Restorative Justice in the Indonesian District Court. Restorative justice values give equal attention to victims and perpetrators. The authority to determine the sense of justice is in the hands of the parties, not the state. They no longer want to be victims again when the state determines the degree of justice that is not in accordance with their wishes as in retributive and restitutive justice.

Musakkir said that restorative justice is a concept of thought that responds to the development of the criminal justice system by focusing on the need for community involvement and victims who feel excluded from the mechanisms that work in the current criminal justice system. On the other hand, restorative justice is also a framework that can be used in responding to a crime for law enforcement and legal workers. Restorative Justice shifted from lex talionis or retributive justice towards an emphasis on efforts to restore the situation, being victim-oriented, giving the perpetrator the opportunity to express his regret to the victim and at the same time showing his responsibility and restoring balance in society. In relation to the prevention of terrorism, the introduction of Restorative Justice in the Indonesian legal system is still partial and not comprehensive, which is spread in various regulatory provisions as well as several practices that have emerged. The application of Restorative Justice is also seen in several law enforcement policies.

In accordance with the Regulation of the Attorney General (Perja) of the Republic of Indonesia Number 15 of 2020 concerning Termination of Prosecution of Cases Based on Restorative Justice, that the termination of prosecution based on Restorative Justice as regulated in the Regulation of the Attorney General's Office (Perja) of the Republic of Indonesia Number 15 of 2020 is a step by the Prosecutor's Office in responding to the legal needs of the community. The problem is, the restoration of the original situation and the balance of protection and interests of victims and perpetrators of criminal acts are not achieved by using the conventional criminal justice system. Meanwhile, the victim will suffer various physical problems or economic losses suffered as a result of the crime. Although the actual crime has been tried, there are a number of consequences that continue to be borne by the victim even after the criminal act has been processed.

Therefore, State Prosecutors are required to pay attention to five things in applying Perja Number 15 of 2020 in carrying out prosecution tasks, namely:

1. Victims' Interests and Other Legal Interests Protected
2. Propriety, decency, and public order.
3. Avoidance of Retaliation
4. Negative Stigma Avoidance
5. Community response and harmony.

Perja Number 15 of 2020 was issued with reference to the provisions of Article 8 paragraph (4) and Article 37 paragraph (1) of Law Number 16 of 2004 concerning the Prosecutors General's Office and Article 42 paragraph (1) of the Draft Criminal Procedure Code (KUHAP).

Referring to Perja No. 15 of 2020, the definition of restorative justice is the settlement of criminal cases by involving the perpetrator, victim, family of the perpetrator/victim, and other related parties to jointly seek a fair solution by emphasizing restoration to its original state, and not retaliation. Currently, the Attorney General's Office does not use Restorative Justice in handling terrorism cases. This is because, in Perja Number 15 of 2020 it is stated that the settlement of criminal cases by prioritizing restorative justice which emphasizes recovery back to its original state and the balance of protection and interests of victims and perpetrators of criminal acts that are not oriented to retaliation is a legal need for society and a mechanism that must be developed in the implementation of the prosecution authority and reform of the criminal justice system.

Termination of prosecution based on restorative justice is carried out on the following principles: justice; public interest; proportionality; punishment as a last resort; and fast, simple, and low cost. Criminal cases can be closed by law and prosecution based on Restorative Justice is terminated if the following conditions are met:

- a. the suspect has committed a crime for the first time;
- b. criminal acts are only punishable by a fine or punishable by imprisonment of not more than 5 (five) years; and
- c. a criminal act is committed with the value of the evidence or the value of the loss caused as a result of the crime of not more than Rp. 2,500,000.00 (two million five hundred thousand rupiah).

Indeed, there are interesting discussions related to terrorism and state threats so that they can be excluded from restorative justice policies, however, the idea of making the handling of terrorism more humane and rooted in local wisdom should be a corrective tool in handling terrorism in Indonesia. Especially when it is associated with the radicalism of terrorism prisoners, the consequences of which lead to revenge, are no longer a matter of ideology, due to the violent handling carried out by law enforcement officers.

C. CONCLUSION

One of the criminal law policies on terrorism is the issuance of Law Number 5 of 2018 concerning Amendments to Law Number 15 of 2003 concerning Eradication of Criminal Acts of Terrorism. In Perja Number 15 of 2020 it is stated that the settlement of criminal cases by prioritizing restorative justice which emphasizes restoration to its original state and the balance of protection and interests of victims and perpetrators of criminal acts that are not oriented to retaliation is a legal need for society and a mechanism that must be built in the implementation of. It is important to encourage the use of limited restorative justice, in order to break the chain of revenge that has been passed down from generation to generation in the handling of terrorism.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to thank the 2021 Indonesian Collaborative Research Program Team, the Ministry of Education and Culture and also to Universitas Sebelas Maret Research and Service Institute.

REFERENCES

- CipiPerdana, "Rekonstruksi Pemidanaan Pelaku Tindak Pidana Terorisme di Indonesia", Volume 23, Nomor 4, Oktober 2016
- Eva Achjani Zulfadan Indriyanto Seno Adji, (2011), "Pergeseran Paradigma Pemidanaan", Bandung: Lubuk Agung
- Muladi. (2002), "Demokrasi Hak Asasi Manusia dan Reformasi Hukum Di Indonesia", Jakarta: Habibie Center
- Firmansyah, Hery. (2011), "Upaya Penanggulangan Tindak Pidana Terorisme di Indonesia", *Mimbar Hukum*, 23(2), 376-393
- George B. Palermo Jianhong Liu (2010), "Restorative Justice and Chinese Traditional Legal Culture in the Context of Contemporary Chinese Criminal Justice Reform", University of Macau, China Southwest University, China, 01-20
- Gordley, J. (2006). Comparative law and legal history. In *The Oxford Handbook of Comparative Law*.
- Gregorius Hermawan Kristyanto, "Fungsi Kejaksaan Dalam Mewujudkan Restorative Justice Dalam Penanganan Anak Berhadapan Dengan Hukum Di Indonesia", *Jurnal Surya Kencana Dua: Dinamika Masalah Hukum dan Keadilan*, Vol. 5, Nomor 1, Juli 2018
- Haposan Sahala Raja Sinaga, "Implementation Of Restorative Justice In Indonesian General Courts (Based On The Decree Of The Director- General Of The Supreme Court Of The Republic Of Indonesia No. 1691/DJU/SK/PS.00/12/2020)", Vol. 9 No. 4 (2021): Volume 9 Issue 4: April 2021
- Harkristuti Harkrisnowo, "Pendekatan Restorative Justice dalam Sosialisasi Rancangan Undang-undang Sistem Peradilan Pidana Anak", 2010.
- Juhari, "Restorative Justice Dalam Pembaharuan Hukum Pidana Di Indonesia", *Jurnal Spektrum Hukum*, Volume 14, Nomor 1, April 2017.

- KuatPujiPrayitno, “*Restorative Justice untuk Peradilan di Indonesia (Prespektif Yuridis Filosofis dalam Penegakan Hukum in Concreto)*”, *Jurnal Dinamika Hukum*, Volume 12, Nomor 3, September 2012
- McCrudden, C. (2017). Legal research and the social sciences. In *Legal Theory and the Social Sciences* (pp. 149-167). Routledge.
- Musakkir, “*Penerapan Prinsip Keadilan Restoratif Terhadap Penyelesaian Perkara Pidana dalam Perspektif Sosiologi Hukum*”. dalam Orasi Penerimaan Jabatan Guru Besar Tetap dalam Ilmu Sosiologi Hukum, Fakultas Hukum Universitas Hasanuddin, Makassar: 12 Juli 2009
- Van Ness, D. W. (2005). Restorative Justice in a Global Perspective [J]. *Journal of Nanjing University (Philosophy, Humanities and Social Sciences)*, 4.
- Winn, M. T. (2020). *Justice on both sides: Transforming education through restorative justice*. Harvard Education Press.

Author Information

Pujiyono

Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta, Indonesia

Seniwati

Universitas Hasanudin, Makasar, Indonesia

Sufmi Dasco Ahmad

Universitas Pakuan, Indonesia

Arfin Sudirman

Universitas Padjajaran, Bandung, Indonesia